

Public Policy and Student Outcomes

Case study prepared for Economics of Government

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Chapter 1: Introduction

Governments worldwide have increasingly been focused on better educating young people over the past few centuries. Almost all countries have compulsory education, enrolment rates are rising and illiteracy is falling. Nevertheless, key aspects of education policy are still heavily debated by researchers and policymakers.

Most people agree that education is important. But to what extent should it be provided with public funds? And how should these funds be allocated, across states, schools and ultimately individual students? How can we ensure that teachers provide students with a quality education, and are there any forms of incentivisation that can assist? What should we teach children, and by what methods? How should education try to prepare young people for the labour market, if at all?

To answer these questions, we need evidence about the effects of education and the effects of policy changes. The most important consequence of education is the outcomes of the students who have received it. These outcomes may be defined in terms of test scores, future income or other notions of wellbeing which might be captured by population surveys. We can analyse these types of indicators to determine the effects of policy, although there are many reasons why this can be challenging to do well, such as lack of data, lack of appropriate experimental design and the difficulty of disentangling causal effects.

These questions also cannot be answered in practice without value judgements, and governments must make these judgements. There may be trade-offs between social equity and economic efficiency. There is a spectrum of views, in which some see education as an essential resource that must be provided by government, and others see it as a product that is best optimised by the interaction of market forces. Whatever view is taken, anticipating the effects of policy requires an understanding of the incentive structures that guide decision making on the part of schools, teachers and students. The empirical evidence can inform this, and should be taken into account when designing policy. Once the expected effects of policy are known, policymakers can decide what they prefer on the basis of their policy objectives.

Many education policies which improve student outcomes appear to come with unintended and undesired side effects. Certain types of policies may have negative effects in developing countries but not in developed ones. The specific design, context and implementation of the policy matter a great deal, and there are always trade-offs. Education should ideally be targeted to the needs and preferences of individual students, and some of the most promising policies attempt to do this, but therefore face nuanced implementation and evaluation issues.

In this case study, we explore the concept of student outcomes through the lens of economics and we examine the evidence about the effects of education policy in a variety of contexts, including Australia. We assess which policies appear to do a good job of improving student outcomes and which do not, and we highlight any unintended side effects of these policies. We note that there are cases where the evidence is too mixed or scarce to make such an assessment, motivating further and more granular research. We explain some implications for the decisions of policymakers.

Chapter 2: What are student outcomes and how do we measure them?

In this paper we examine the effects of various policies on student outcomes. The notion of student outcomes broadly refers to the performance and wellbeing of students. The outcome of a policy is the result of its 'outputs', which are any products or services generated by that policy (OECD 2002, Formstone 2012). For example, the number of students taught in a given course would be considered an output, whereas their average grade would be a measure of the outcome. Outcomes may be considered at the level of individuals or aggregated up to provide information about larger populations, such as families, communities or nations. Studying results across different demographic groups can reveal nuance about whom the policy is benefiting and whom it might be ignoring or even harming. Examining student outcomes can provide useful information about the strengths and weaknesses of the education process. With such an evidence base, education practitioners and policymakers can propose and implement methods to improve these outcomes in an informed manner. It is important to ensure that measures of student outcomes are observable and easy to define, and allow for comparison between students.

This chapter introduces the concept of student outcomes – in particular, how they are measured and how we can evaluate their determinants. In Chapter 3, we explore the importance of student outcomes and motivate why policymakers should care about them, especially in terms of wellbeing. In Chapter 4, we set up the economic case for government intervention in education. Chapters 5 and 6 discuss empirical research on the impacts on student outcomes from policies that have been implemented around the world, in developing and developed countries respectively. We focus on the questions of which policies work well and which do not, and how this can vary with economic and political circumstances. Finally, in Chapter 7, we turn this analysis to the case of Australia.

How do we measure student outcomes?

The question of how best to measure student outcomes first depends on our overall methodological framework. Gathering and analysing data about student outcomes may involve either quantitative, qualitative or mixed methods (i.e. a mix of quantitative and qualitative) techniques. Quantitative measures, such as standardised test results, are used to measure academic outcomes. However, as researchers have increasingly incorporated considerations about non-academic outcomes into their work, qualitative data have played a supplementary role. Qualitative data may include unstructured information gathered from teacher reports and interviews, or classroom observations (Kennedy 1999). Qualitative methods are applied on a smaller sample than quantitative methods, but can provide insights into the human experience and individuals' underlying motivations when they react to a given policy intervention (Fleming & Fitzgerald 2009, p. 176).

The strength of quantitative methods lies in their ability to test hypotheses and make inferences, which is not possible in the qualitative framework—see Breunig (2018). Quantitative research allows for estimation of the strength, direction and significance of the relationships between policy inputs (including funding) and outputs or outcomes (Monroe 2000, pp. 98-99). This is crucial for policymakers, who regularly need to know what the expected result of a given policy would be, and therefore whether it is justified to spend money on such a policy, and what the size of any expenditure should be. In practice, qualitative methods are most useful for making observations about the context of a policy, generating hypotheses which can then be tested with quantitative techniques, and gathering

anecdotes which may assist policymakers in humanising policy impacts and explaining them to relevant decision makers. Throughout this paper, we focus on evidence collected from quantitative rather than qualitative research to examine the determinants of student outcomes and analyse relevant policies.

The concept of student outcomes can include several different dimensions. Many organisations and experts think about student outcomes in terms of achievement in academic domains such as numeracy and literacy, as measured through test scores, minimum proficiency levels, IQ scores and course grades. However, there also many possible non-academic indicators, relating to things like students' attitudes and levels of motivation, acquisition of essential life skills, perceived learning and transformative changes experienced by students (Wilson & Ryan 2013, Cotton & Wikelund 1989, UNESCO 2019). The OECD (2010) has conducted numerous studies on non-academic student outcomes among its member nations. Some findings include that 85 per cent of those with tertiary education are likely to be employed, and that there is a positive relationship between educational attainment and social wellbeing. Moreno, Ovalle and Vicari (2012) confirm these findings and consider further related measures of student outcomes such as those relating to communication and leadership skills. Many researchers (e.g. Stasulane 2017) propose happiness, life satisfaction, and psychological wellbeing as additionally important non-academic student outcomes. Non-academic student outcomes tend to be harder to measure than academic outcomes, but are no less important. Of course, academic and non-academic measures are not independent of each other. On average, higher test scores and higher educational achievement should lead to increased present and future wellbeing across other dimensions, including higher wages.

There is an important distinction between measures of student outcomes which are immediate and short-term, such as test scores, and those which relate to the longer-term effects of education, such as future employment. While of key interest to researchers, and especially economists, studies on longer-term effects are particularly challenging due to the multiplicity of other influencing factors besides education. Researchers must attempt to control for these factors. Even in the absence of this consideration, it is difficult to form a complete picture of how future outcomes of current students are determined, because education has substantial and durable non-wage benefits which are harder to measure.

How do we evaluate the impact of policy on student outcomes?

Within the quantitative framework, there are a few approaches to analysing policy impacts. Researchers may use experimental settings such as randomised controlled trials (RCTs) to determine the exogenous impacts of education by differentiating outcomes between a randomly assigned treatment group and a control group. However, such studies are expensive to run and may suffer from problems of external validity—that is, the results may be very informative about the policy as tested in a specific experimental setting, but less informative about wider implications of the policy outside of that setting. It is also easy to imagine experimental designs which could be very useful but highly unethical, such as measuring what would happen if a group of students were deliberately denied access to important educational resources. For these reasons, researchers often instead use data collected from 'natural experiments', or historical events which provided conditions that were broadly similar to an RCT.

Econometric techniques may be used to derive causal effects in relationships between education and student outcomes from natural experiments. For example, Card and Krueger (1996) use the results of a natural experiment to estimate the impact of education on wages

via difference-in-differences techniques. The natural experiment was characterised by differences between North and South Carolina in terms of the levels of school resources provided to black students and white students during the segregation era. The authors focus on the pupil-teacher ratio within classes as an indicator. Their work provides evidence that resources given to schools can have a significant impact on the future financial outcomes of students. However, the authors do make the usual caveat that it is difficult to draw causal inferences from observational data.

The importance of data

The ability to make valid inferences about the effects of policy on student outcomes is dependent on the scope and quality of the underlying data. In Australia, the Australian National Assessment Program – Literacy and Numeracy (NAPLAN) is often used to measure and compare student outcomes at the national level, including for Indigenous students as a group. A recent example of a national study using NAPLAN is that of Goss and Sonnemann (2018), who exploit the comprehensiveness of this data source to compare student performance between states. They note that it is the best dataset for their purpose available at scale, despite further improvements being possible in its level of detail and accuracy.

Some research questions are only able to be investigated given the availability of a certain type of data. There are features of data which can be especially useful to harness in understanding the determinants of student outcomes. Longitudinal data on individual students or educational institutions, when consistently measured and collected over time, allow for assessing changes in trends over time and are important in understanding causal relationships. They also allow for a greater understanding of effects over a person's lifecycle – such as the effect of schooling experiences on wages and wellbeing later in life. Datasets that include socio-demographic information, and other important factors that may affect a young person's growth, are useful as they allow researchers to isolate the effects of schooling from other factors, or to compare how policy interventions might affect different demographic groups of students.

The ability to link different datasets together can be a great asset to researchers. Ideally, such a link is exact, whereby an entity in one dataset directly and identifiably corresponds to an entity in the other dataset. However, linkages may also be estimated via probabilistic methods or data imputation. Administrative data collected by governments (such as official data relating to taxes and transfers) can contribute to a much more accurate and granular understanding of a population, and there can be significant advantages of linking other datasets, such as survey or academic test score data, to these records. Similarly, any linkages that can be made to school- and teacher-level data allow for a greater and more detailed understanding of the education process.

International standards for student outcomes

There are a range of international standards with which student outcomes can be measured. These form an important part of the evidence base regarding educational outcomes, because they allow for direct comparison of results between countries. The eight Millennium Development Goals constituted the overall development framework of the UN during the period between 2000 and 2015; achieving universal primary education was one of the goals – and during this period, net enrolment in primary education in developing countries improved from 83 per cent to 91 per cent (UN 2015a). The UN's current development agenda is comprised of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which includes the goal of “ensuring inclusive and equitable quality education and promoting lifelong learning opportunities for

all”, and this encompasses all levels of education (early childhood, primary, secondary, tertiary) (UNESCO 2019).

Figure 1 depicts the SDG indicators of proficiency in mathematics and reading at the lower secondary level in selected countries in 2015. These indicators measure the proportion of children and young people achieving a minimum proficiency level in mathematics and reading. The data in the chart are largely composed of observations from the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), augmented with national data and data from the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS). The strongest-performing countries on the basis of these measures are Singapore, South Korea and Vietnam and the weakest are Indonesia, Brazil and Colombia.

There are several other sources of data on education systems in different countries, including the OECD. Figure 2 depicts enrolment rates for 18-year-olds and rates of graduation from the upper secondary level over a person’s lifetime, for 14 out of the 18 countries from Figure 1. These are not particularly reliable measures of student outcomes. In contrast to the SDG indicators, they do not provide standardised information about student performance. The achievement of graduation may mean meeting vastly different performance criteria across different countries. However, these measures may give a broad sense of the ability of an education system to deliver student outcomes by attracting and retaining secondary school students. The Netherlands and Russia rank highest in enrolment rates, whereas Greece and South Korea rank highest in graduation rates. Again, the lowest-performing countries are Indonesia, Brazil and Colombia.

Figure 1: Proficiency in mathematics and reading at the lower secondary level in selected countries (UN 2019)

Figure 2: Net enrolment rate for 18-year-olds and upper secondary graduation rate (OECD 2018a, 2018b)

Assessment framework	Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA)	Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS)	Progress in International Reading and Literacy Study (PIRLS)
Year coverage	Every three years since 2000	Every four years since 1995	Every five years since 2001
Age group	15 year old students	Fourth and eighth grades	Fourth grade
Focus subjects	Reading, mathematics, science, collaborative problem solving, financial literacy	Mathematics and science	Reading
Carried out by	OECD	International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA)	IEA
Number of countries	79	64	61
Aim	Assessing whether what was learnt can be applied to real life situations (skills-based)	Monitoring trends in math and science (curriculum based)	Monitoring trends in reading (curriculum based)

Table 1: Summary of international indicators on student outcomes (OECD 2018c, IEA 2019a, IEA 2019b)

Standardised international indicators, such as the SDG indicators, exist to assess the education systems of different countries. A summary of three major international indicators is provided in Table 1. In addition, there are regional assessment frameworks such as the Southern and Eastern Africa Consortium for Monitoring Educational Quality, and the Analysis Programme of the CONFEMEN Education Systems in Africa (Education Policy Data Center 2012).

Conclusion

Countries and non-governmental organisations invest large amounts of time and money in educational programs. How can we tell if these investments represent value for money? First, we need to define the outcomes that we are attempting to influence. Second, we need to gather data that inform us about these outcomes. Data need to include information that allows us to identify the effects of policy and also to identify differential effects on different sub-groups of interest in the population. Quantitative statistical techniques offer the most promise for identifying the causal impacts of policy but identifying policy impacts is not always straightforward. Qualitative methods can provide important information to supplement and inform quantitative analysis. Internationally standardised measures of student outcomes may be used to compare performance between countries – these include: progress towards SDGs, and the PISA, TIMSS and PIRLS frameworks.

Chapter 3: Why should we care about student outcomes? Examining the relationship between wellbeing and other measures of student outcomes

This chapter examines the relationship between individual and societal wellbeing and other measures of student outcomes. Our intention is to demonstrate that the effects of positive student outcomes in the form of test scores and completion of higher grade levels, or less tangible attributes such as development of social skills and motivation to learn, can be substantial and far-reaching. This, combined with the economic arguments to be outlined in Chapter 4, sets up a compelling case for policy interventions to ensure strong educational outcomes. We begin this chapter by discussing how individual wellbeing is measured. We then evaluate the effects on wellbeing when some typical student outcome measures are improved. Finally, we analyse the broader societal implications relating to income, the wider economy, civic participation, equity and social mobility.

Indicators of individual wellbeing

While wellbeing might seem like an intuitive and straightforward idea, it becomes clear that it is complex and multi-dimensional when we consider measuring it. There are many possible indicators and different paradigms that attempt to address this problem (OECD 2017a, p. 60; Borgonovi & Pál 2016). Over the last decade, and particularly since the global financial crisis, there has been an increased focus on measuring wellbeing not purely as a financial concept, but also incorporating other aspects of quality of life, including education and skills (OECD 2017b, p. 22). Figure 3 captures such a conceptualisation of individual wellbeing. Improvement of community wellbeing is also an area of increasing interest for economists (Dalziel, Saunders & Saunders 2018, p. 2).

Figure 3: OECD framework for measuring wellbeing (OECD 2017b)

The relationship between student outcomes and current wellbeing of students

To measure the current wellbeing of students, it is common to use indicators such as self-reported motivation to achieve, a sense of belonging at school and exercise habits (OECD 2017a). Figure 4 depicts the OECD framework of student wellbeing. Student wellbeing is influenced by multiple immediate or “proximal” factors, including the school experience, family and communities. The OECD considers education policy to be a “contextual” source of student wellbeing.

Student wellbeing is an important noncognitive outcome of schooling. Enhanced student wellbeing may lead to improved academic achievement in four main ways: by increasing student motivation to participate and achieve, by increasing student engagement and participation in learning, by increasing student attendance and therefore school completion, and by encouraging positive behaviour at school and therefore decreasing levels of suspension and exclusion from school (ACU & Erebus 2008, p. 67). This relationship between current wellbeing of students and improved academic achievement can be mutually reinforcing.

Figure 4: Dimensions and sources of student wellbeing (OECD 2017a, p. 62)

The relationship between student outcomes and future wellbeing of students

Economists tend to emphasise the longer-term and more persistent effects of education on wellbeing in their research, rather than just the current wellbeing of students, which may not persist. These longer-term benefits to individuals may affect society as a whole in profound ways. For example, increased student wellbeing leads to increased workforce participation and higher productivity (ACU & Erebus 2008, p. 67). It also provides benefits to the individual and society which extend beyond the production process or the labour market (Lochner 2011, p. 183; Grossman 2006, p. 591). We now briefly introduce some of the evidence on the longer-term effects of positive student outcomes over the dimensions of physical and social wellbeing.

Providing physically and mentally stimulating activities to children in the years between preschool and third grade, combined with different forms of parental support, appears to result in better educational outcomes and later reduce the incidence of depression during young adulthood (Ormel, Lindenberg, Steverink & Verbrugge 1999). Reynolds et al. (2007) demonstrate this empirically using a longitudinal quasi-experiment with 1539 participants. Recent research suggests that early childhood interventions that boost noncognitive skills and encourage motivation have a positive influence on proxies for young people's wellbeing (Heckman 2000, Heckman & Rubinstein 2001). In general, enjoyment and engagement in education can exert a tangible influence on future life satisfaction and attainment of opportunities (Scharf, Hadjar & Grecu 2019, p. 852).

In terms of social wellbeing, positive student outcomes can contribute to status, behavioural confirmation and affection (Ormel et al., p. 68). Status may be achieved through the

obtainment of educational credentials and qualifications (Scharf et al. 2019, p. 852), which often determine future occupations and prestige. Behavioural confirmation is valued by students, as they attempt to meet the expectations and aspirations of parents, as well as to develop positive relationships within their peer groups. When school is perceived as a positive emotional setting in which students can feel accepted, their needs for affection are also satisfied within this setting. Jones, Brown and Aber (2011) study the two-year impacts of a program that couples social-emotional development with literacy (“Reading, Writing, Respect and Resolution”), via a school-randomised experimental design including 1184 children in 18 elementary schools. The authors find evidence of reduced levels of hostile attributional bias (i.e. a tendency to make false assumptions that others have harmful intent), aggressive behaviour and depression, and improvements in attention skills and socially competent behaviour as a result of the intervention. They also find that students identified by teachers to be at the highest behavioural risk exhibited increased achievement in mathematics and reading following the intervention. While the authors’ immediate findings refer to the initial two years following the intervention, they note an expectation on the basis of related literature for some effects to persist far beyond this period.

The relationship between student outcomes and societal wellbeing

We have seen that positive student outcomes result in increased individual wellbeing of students, and that the benefits of this phenomenon may extend much further into the future for those individuals. In the remainder of this chapter, we explore the relationship between student outcomes and key economic and social indicators that represent aspects of longer-term wellbeing at a broader societal level. We focus on four themes: income and wealth, economic growth, civic participation, and equity and social mobility.

Income and wealth

Income and wealth are important indicators of individual wellbeing (Diener, Sandvik, Seidlitz & Diener 1993). Research has found that education is positively correlated with income and wealth (Harmon, Oosterbeck & Walker 2003; Teixeira 2014; Desjardins 2008; Buchanan, Finegold, Mayhew & Warhurst 2017). People who are more highly educated and skilled tend to earn more than others (Becker 1975), which leads to greater wellbeing. Rational choice theory indicates that a higher income results in higher utility or wellbeing as dictated by an individual’s utility function. Human capital theory suggests that education generates skills which increase a person’s future labour productivity, measured by output per hour of work (Hu & Wolniak 2010, Dalziel et al. 2018).

Some economists believe that the number of years spent in school can affect an individual’s future earnings, independently of any skills that individual gained during that time. This is partly because employers rely on qualifications and credentials as positive signals when making hiring decisions (Mayer 1999). However, there are probably also direct benefits from more years spent in education. A higher level of education has been found to have a positive correlation with cognitive ability (Stiglitz 1975), student engagement in college (Hu & Wolniak 2010) and higher academic grades (Becker & Rosen 1992). These factors influence other measures of student outcomes and future earnings in the labour market. Overall, despite some unknowns about causality in these relationships, positive correlations indicate that enhanced student outcomes may lead to increases in future income or wealth. Therefore, a more highly educated population should on the whole have an increased quality of life.

Economic growth

A key measure of wellbeing at the macroeconomic level is economic growth (Barro 1991). Student outcomes as proxies for human capital have long been associated with economic growth (Barro 1991). People who are more highly educated improve national labour productivity because they are better able to solve problems, use new technologies, innovate and adapt to change (Banerjee & Wilson 2016, p. 48). Additionally, the social returns of a more highly educated population are greater than the sum of individual returns (Psacharopoulos & Patrinos 2018).

As with the measure of income, there is some debate over whether economic growth is tied to quantity or quality of schooling (Benos & Zotou 2014). Using regression analysis on historical economic and education data, Barro (1991) finds a positive correlation between enrolment rates and GDP growth in the years between 1965 and 1985. In a follow-up study using the same time period, he finds correlations between GDP growth and male secondary school attainment, and GDP growth and women's primary school attainment (Barro 2001). Krueger and Lindahl (2001) find large social returns to increases in average levels of schooling over 10 to 20 year periods. The authors also find that higher initial levels of schooling appear to only be correlated with growth in developing countries. On the other hand, more recent studies have found a relatively weak relationship, if any, between duration of schooling and economic growth (Delgado, Henderson & Parmeter 2014; Woessmann 2016, pp. 7-8). On the basis of cross-country comparisons of the OECD's PISA scores, such studies have found that economic growth is more highly correlated with cognitive skills than duration of schooling (Woessmann 2016, Hanushek 2013). Hanushek and Woessmann (2012) find in general that a 25 point improvement in PISA scores increases the expected GDP growth rate by half a percentage point. This impact may be mediated by domestic institutional factors, which may include incentives to rent seek or engage in otherwise economically unproductive labour (Pritchett 2001, pp. 382-384).

Civic participation

Civic participation is considered an indicator of wellbeing. The link between student outcomes and civic participation has been highlighted by a number of scholars (Campbell 2006, Kaase & Marsh 1979, Galston 2004). Campbell points out that education is related to social capital. Campbell and Galston also suggest that highly educated citizens tend to engage more in civic and political affairs. They participate in public policy mechanisms more often than less educated citizens. A more educated population is more likely to have an understanding of their individual interests in the context of the political processes occurring around them (Galston 2004, p. 264). In many democracies, education therefore plays a central role in bolstering civic engagement (Kaase & Marsh 1979, as cited in Campbell 2006, p. 26).

The importance of the relationship between student outcomes and civic participation is emphasised in a study by Herdiana (2019) in Indonesia. Herdiana finds that low-income families in Indonesia tend to not participate in village development. They are more likely to prioritise meeting their basic needs for survival, even though government regulation requires them to be involved in these local planning activities (Herdiana 2019, p. 8). Education can provide students with the skills to engage with such civic issues. Students who have the opportunity to actively engage in discussion about local development issues during their education will be able to take part more effectively in future policy decision making processes (Carnegie Corporation of New York & CIRCLE 2003).

Equity and social mobility

Equity and social mobility are key aspects of both individual and societal wellbeing, and are highly correlated with education. This is particularly true of marginalised demographic groups and women (Wodon, Montenegro, Nguyen & Onagoruwa 2018, pp. 8-9), who experience lower rates of educational attainment globally (Narayan & Van der Weide 2018, p. 156). Women typically make up a large part of the informal 'grey' market and manual labour force. Educational qualifications can provide a vehicle for their financial independence, and are linked to improved health outcomes and personal agency (Wodon et al. 2018, p. 4). Education policy can therefore be an important tool in the pursuit of social empowerment.

Student outcomes are particularly relevant for equity and social mobility in developing countries. Despite earlier studies indicating that factors other than education are more significant in generating academic achievement, Heyneman (1976) finds that in developing countries the opposite is typically true. The quality of education is found to have a much greater impact on the later economic position of underprivileged individuals in developing countries than in developed ones (Buchmann & Hannum 2001, p. 82). According to Heyneman and Loxely (1983, p. 1163), "the poorer the country", the stronger the correlation between education and achievement.

Conclusion

In this chapter, we have outlined the positive impacts of enhanced student outcomes on current and future student wellbeing. Researchers have increasingly acknowledged the importance of non-financial dimensions of wellbeing, despite these being harder to measure quantitatively. There seems to be a mutually reinforcing relationship between current student outcomes and wellbeing indicators, although causality is hard to demonstrate clearly. We have also outlined some compelling reasons on a broader scale as to why policymakers should care about developing policies to improve student outcomes.

Enhanced student wellbeing provides the foundation for future academic success. From academic success stem benefits to both the individual and community. For the individual, human capital is developed, leading to higher projected income and better equity and social mobility outcomes; for society, this leads to higher GDP, formation of social capital and increased civic participation. Therefore, there are many reasons for policymakers to care about student outcomes beyond the benefits to the individual student. In the following chapter, we will examine in greater detail the economic rationale for government intervention in education.

Chapter 4: What is the rationale for government intervention in education?

Education has some characteristics of a private good. If a person obtains a degree, that individual benefits from the degree in terms of higher wages and higher levels of wellbeing and happiness, as seen in Chapter 3. People can be expected to invest in their own education for the purpose of increasing individual productivity and future earnings.

Education also clearly has social benefits that spill over beyond the individual who gets the education. Broad literacy is important to economic productivity and to the proper functioning of a modern democracy. It is additionally fairly clear that there are important market failures that arise in education, meaning that society misses out on many of these benefits when private markets alone are tasked with providing education. These market failures are linked to asymmetric information, principal-agent problems and credit constraints. Further, we could argue on moral grounds that education should be provided to all irrespective of ability to pay. Education may therefore be seen as a merit good – one that is beneficial enough for society in a broader sense that it is deserving of government intervention to ensure sufficient and equitable distribution.

The positive externalities and market failures associated with education, as well as the status of education as a merit good, provide a strong rationale for government intervention in education. In this chapter, we discuss these issues and introduce some examples of ways in which they can be addressed with public policy.

Positive externalities of education

Education is a good that provides far-reaching and long-term benefits. Clearly, even education at the early childhood level has a significant impact on the future welfare of children, and also on the welfare of their local community and society as a whole (Friedman 1982; see also Chapter 3). A more educated population not only exhibits greater wellbeing but is also more economically productive.

Since the 1970s, western countries have increasingly used education to address large-scale and complex problems in society. It is believed that school education can promote broadly desired behaviours among citizens, which may lead to an increased sense of social values and social acceptance, and also economic growth. Education plays a crucial role in the success of democratic institutions – motivating civic engagement, encouraging participation in democracy and discouraging the state from pursuing a dictatorship (Glaeser & Ponzetto 2007, p. 77). And the equitable distribution of education can help break the poverty cycle, which is even more important for developing countries (UN 2015b).

These large positive externalities of education provide a rationale for government intervention. In the absence of intervention, there will be a suboptimal allocation of resources across the economy. One way of explaining this phenomenon is that market prices do not accurately reflect the marginal social costs of producing education, probably leading to an undersupply. Government, however, can factor social costs into market transactions. In the case of education policy, this might take the form of subsidising certain costs associated with education to factor in the social benefits to education which are not taken into account by the market alone.

Market failures associated with education

We now outline three further types of market failure which may provide grounds for intervention: asymmetric information, principal-agent problems and credit constraints.

Asymmetric information refers to the situation where agents on one or both sides of a market possess incomplete information on the nature of a transaction. In the education setting, parents often need to make decisions based on limited information. While parents can examine the test performance of a school, they may not have a good understanding of things like class size or styles of teaching, and the effects these factors might have on their children. Given this lack of knowledge, parents may choose education based on what worked for them, what is recommended by friends or family, or for convenience. If this occurs on a larger scale, the result may be an inefficient allocation of resources.

Education may be subject to the principal-agent problem, another source of market failure wherein parents (the 'agent') acting on behalf of a child (the 'principal') pursue an agenda separate from the best interests of the child. For example, as only some portion of the returns to schooling will accrue to parents, households may underinvest in schooling. Mill (1859) therefore argues that in the case of parental neglect, it is the role of the state to intervene to require adequate schooling.

Credit constraints provide an additional rationale for government intervention. Students from poor families who have promising educational futures may not be able to obtain credit from standard credit markets in the absence of collateral. Their ability to work hard and succeed in the future may not convince banks to lend them money for education today. The Higher Education Contribution Scheme (HECS) in Australia is an example of a policy which effectively mitigates this problem, allowing for easy access to high quality tertiary education for all students, regardless of any credit constraints. The system offers government loans for education with a repayment plan contingent on future income. This latter aspect provides an element of insurance against default. HECS is a good example of a 'hybrid' policy, or a policy that involves the public and private sectors cooperating in a mutually beneficial manner (Chapman 2018).

Why should governments try to correct market failure?

We have seen that education comes with significant positive externalities but may suffer from several types of market failure, in which resources are allocated inefficiently across the economy by the private market. Effective government intervention designed to address market failure produces more efficient and more equitable outcomes. Equity concerns arise when there is a significant discrepancy between groups in access to a resource within society. According to the OECD (2012), the promotion of equity within education results in a net benefit to society, and better social outcomes. In practice, making evaluations about equity is not straightforward – it is hard to formulate an appropriate standard of equity and then to assess whether this standard has been achieved.

There is sometimes (but not always) a trade-off between equity and efficiency in policy design, where increasing one reduces the other. Hybrid policies often provide the best solution with regard to both efficiency and equity. In the case of HECS, the result is greater equity, because the government is providing universal access to education, but also greater efficiency, as the public sector is not delivering this resource itself, but enabling the market to do so – and this

allows for propagation of the benefits of education throughout the economy to an extent which otherwise would not have been possible.

Education as a merit good

A third argument for government intervention, on moral rather than economic grounds, is that education is a merit good. A merit good is “a commodity that ought to be subsidised or provided free on a basis other than consumer choice, because it is judged that an individual should not have it on the basis of ability and/or willingness to pay” (Daviet 2016, p. 3).

Viewing education as a merit good provides a strong rationale for ensuring at least a minimum level of access to education to all members of society.

Correcting market failures with policy

There are a number of policy tools available to governments to correct for education market failures. The effectiveness of these policies and their application in developing and developed countries is discussed in the final three chapters, but we first introduce some ideas in the remainder of this chapter.

The most prominent type of policy to correct for education market failure is the use of subsidies to mitigate undersupply by lessening the financial burden borne by educational institutions or education recipients. Subsidies help to ensure that the same opportunities to access education are available to all children, thereby also leading to improved student outcomes (Tilak 2005, p. 1). A classical education subsidy consists of tuition vouchers, where the government transfers money to parents on the condition that the voucher will be spent on schooling. Another option is a tax credit system, which reduces the tax liability of parents to support their children’s education (Hungerman & Rinz 2016, p. 1). Alternatively, the subsidy can be provided directly to schools – to assist with employment of teachers or provision of other educational resources to students, as has been the case in Argentina (McEwan 2002, p. 2). Other mechanisms of public support for education may include specific funding allocated to scholarships or school infrastructure. A related point is that the more financially involved a government is in providing education, the more authority it likely has over curricula and other features of the education system that can contribute to student outcomes (Poterba 1996, p. 15).

An example of a successful government intervention that addresses market failure is the Head Start program in the US, which has been credited with lifting student outcomes for millions of children (Ludwig & Phillips 2008, p. 257). Head Start provides low-income children aged between three and five with social welfare services, dietary needs, health services and schooling. The program was launched in 1965 as part of President Lyndon B Johnson’s “war on poverty”, and is one of America’s longest running school programs. Deming (2009) analyses the outcomes of children participating in Head Start between 1984 and 1990. He finds long term benefits associated with the program, equivalent to around 0.23 standard deviations of a summary index of young adult outcomes, and with larger impacts for relatively more disadvantaged children. This corresponds to closing nearly one third of the gap in outcomes between the bottom family income quartile and the median. Deming finds that basing conclusions regarding the success of the program around current test scores alone greatly understates the benefit of the program, and generally advocates that researchers take a longer-term viewpoint when evaluating interventions. His research demonstrates that Head Start is a good government intervention with large positive externalities which private markets

alone would have been unable to generate. In Chapter 6, we explore further policy solutions to improve student outcomes in developed countries.

Conclusion

In this chapter, we have outlined the strong case for government intervention in education. Not only is education a good thing for individuals, but its benefits for society and the economy are significant and far-reaching. As private markets on their own are incapable of providing education to society in an equitable and efficient manner, government intervention is arguably required. Examining specific sources of market failure such as asymmetric information, principal-agent problems and credit constraints can help us understand what goes wrong in a purely market-oriented system and what steps government may need to take to ensure that education is optimally provided. We have seen that there are several different forms of subsidisation, whereby the government provides funds or resources either to education recipients directly, or to institutions – and that these can work well, taking the example of the Head Start program in the US. HECS in Australia is a successful example of a ‘hybrid’ policy which effectively loosens credit constraints, enabling students to obtain government loans for tertiary education which are accessible to all, affordable and insured against default. Education is then provided by the market which is also subject to some government regulation.

Chapter 5: What policies have been proposed to increase student outcomes in developing countries, and how effective have they been?

Throughout the majority of human history, economic growth has been absent, incomes have been low, and lifespans have been short. In general, humans these days live longer, healthier and wealthier lives. Improvements in education, training, and knowledge diffusion within and between economies have been fundamental to this relatively rapid transition. In this chapter, we examine some examples of education policies in developing countries and we analyse their effectiveness in terms of improving student outcomes. We focus on example studies from Argentina and Uganda. We find that the policies of decentralisation of education in Argentina and provision of free primary education in Uganda have been broadly successful in lifting student outcomes. We also note the lessons learnt from aspects of the policies that did not work as well as intended.

Overview of education policies in developing countries

In this section, we introduce some of the main types of policies to improve student outcomes that can be implemented in developing countries, along with findings from the literature about their impacts. Ganimian and Murnane (2016) assess results from 223 impact evaluation studies of education policies in 56 low and lower-middle income countries between 2000 and 2015. The authors highlight four key lessons regarding education policies in developing countries, which are outlined in Table 2. They are subject to the caveat that there was some heterogeneity in conclusions across studies, partly attributable to a large diversity in methodology.

Table 2: Findings from education policy evaluation studies in developing countries (Ganimian & Murnane 2016)

Finding	Example study that illustrates this finding
Reducing the costs of going to school and providing alternatives to traditional public schools increases attendance and attainment, but does not consistently increase student achievement.	Study: Barrera-Osorio, Linden and Urquiola (2007) Context: Bogota, Colombia in 2004 Policy: School fees reduced Result: Enrolment increased, but sudden influx of students put strain on public systems
Providing parents with information about school quality and returns to schooling generally improves student attainment and achievement.	Study: Jensen (2010) Context: Dominican Republic in 2001 Policy: Information provided to parents about wages of adults with different levels of education Result: Years of schooling completed increased
Providing more or better resources to students does not improve student achievement unless this changes children's daily experiences at school.	Study: Glewwe, Kremer and Moulin (2009) Context: Kenya in 1995 Policy: Free English, mathematics and science textbooks provided to students Result: No impact as books were in English (third language for many students)

<p>Implementing well-designed incentives for teachers increases their motivation and student achievement in very low performance settings.</p>	<p>Study: Glewwe, Ilias and Kremer (2010) Context: Busia and Teso, Kenya in 1997 Policy: Teachers incentivised with prizes linked to student scores on certain tests Result: Teachers taught to the test, which improved test performance but not subject performance</p>
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Further to the above policy lessons, Ganimian and Murnane (2016) point to promising evidence on policies that encourage methods of education that address students’ individual learning needs – for example, by helping teachers personalise instruction, providing additional help to struggling students, or letting students learn at their own pace. Particularly effective examples of this include a class size reduction policy in Kenya (Duflo, Dupas & Kremer 2011), a policy of grouping students by measured ability level and tailoring education to their level in India (Duflo, Berry, Mukerji & Shotland 2015), and offering additional remedial support to low-achieving students in India (Banerjee, Cole, Duflo & Linden 2007).

We must note that there is no one-size-fits-all approach to implementing education reform. While the findings presented in this chapter provide a useful guide to things that work and things that do not work, the context needs to be carefully considered. Factors such as cultural, environmental, political and economic concerns, as well as those regarding individual needs of parents or children, can be highly influential in determining policy outcomes. What works in one country may not work in another. Understanding this, the remainder of this chapter covers two broadly successful policies that were implemented in developing countries to improve education outcomes.

Example study: School decentralisation in Argentina

During the 1990s, a trend emerged in Latin America of market-driven restructuring of the state and integration with the world economy, as promoted by international organisations such as the IMF and the World Bank. In Argentina, this process included modernisation of education and other social sectors (Minujin & Kessler 1995). In 1991, the Argentinian central government transferred control of federal secondary schools to local governments (Galiani, Gertler & Schargrotsky 2008, p. 2109). Provincial governments took on the bulk of governance responsibilities for the formerly national school system, including budget, resource allocation, and personnel decisions. The federal government was charged with establishing minimum curriculum requirements, providing technical assistance, supervising teacher training programs, and administering standardised tests. Evidence on the effectiveness of this policy has been positive but mixed. The policy has had a positive impact on student outcomes, as measured by student test scores, but these benefits have not been uniformly shared across municipalities.

Rationale for decentralisation of education policy

There are five main reasons for governments to enact a policy of decentralisation in education, according to Prawda (1993):

- *Transferring the burden to local governments:* Decentralisation allows central governments to transfer the cost burden of education to local governments and communities. The involvement of local governments may allow for an increase in the level of resources allocated to education.

- *Efficiency*: Decentralised units of government can allocate resources in a more productive way and can be more easily held accountable for their decisions.
- *Quality*: Local governments can better tailor specific features of the education system to match regional characteristics, including those specific to certain groups of students.
- *Redistribution of power*: Decentralisation can empower local governments and diffuse the power that central governments hold.
- *Stability*: Conflict may be reduced as systems are insulated from the central government. Increased democratisation of education can empower parents, teachers and local communities in decision-making processes (Lauglo 1995, McGinn 1992).

Positive effects on national test scores

The policy of decentralisation of education had a positive impact on student test scores. Specifically, mathematics test scores increased by 3.7 per cent and Spanish test scores rose by 5.1 per cent on average after five years of decentralised administration (Galiani et al. 2008). These tests are nationally standardised, being administered by the National Education Ministry to all secondary school students in their fifth (final) year. While test scores cannot capture all dimensions of student outcomes (see Chapter 2), they are easy to measure and still highly informative.

Equity considerations

While student outcomes improved as a result of the decentralisation policy, this did not occur uniformly across municipalities. The positive effects of decentralisation did not occur in poor municipalities, so only schools in non-poor municipalities saw the benefits from the policy. This increased inequality in education outcomes likely flows through into future earnings (Galiani et al. 2008). It is difficult to know the reason for this effect, but one explanation is that non-poor communities were able to capture more resources from their provincial governments as a result of their greater influence. Their already greater resources may have enabled them to more effectively campaign for further resources. It is also possible that non-poor communities have a stronger preference for education provision relative to other public goods.

The key takeaway here is that decentralisation can be an effective policy to improve the provision of education to students in terms of student outcomes. However, care should be taken to ensure that disadvantaged communities are not left behind – this requires a well-defined understanding of how resources are allocated at a provincial level, and whether there are any mechanisms that might prevent proper access to resources in disadvantaged communities.

Example study: Universal Primary Education and capitation grant in Uganda

Similar to Argentina, the 1990s in Uganda was a period of education reform. This followed many years of civil war and withdrawal of government funding for public services. Of particular significance was the introduction of a Universal Primary Education (UPE) program in 1997, which removed user fees in public primary schools so that primary education became free of charge. The UPE program was developed based on the UN's (2007) Millennium Development Goal of achieving UPE for all school-aged children, regardless of economic status. The program was supported by a capitation grant (i.e. provision of additional funding to primary schools based on the number of students enrolled) provided by the government to schools, which was intended to replace school fees (Nishimura et al. 2009). The grant was provided at the rate of 4,000 Uganda shillings per pupil per year for all government-aided primary schools, with a threshold cost for each school of 100,000 Uganda shillings per month over a nine-month

period annually (Ugandan Ministry of Education and Sports 2008). The education reforms in Uganda raised total education expenditure from 2.1 per cent of GDP in 1995 to 4.8 per cent of GDP in 2000, and the share of the education sector in the national budget increased from 13.7 per cent in 1990 to 24.7 per cent in 1998 (ODI 2005). We now discuss the evidence regarding the effects of these reforms.

Positive effects of UPE

The main positive effects of UPE were increases in primary school enrolment and attendance. Enrolment was increased by 4.4 million between 1997 and 2008 (from 3.1 million in 1997 to 7.5 million in 2008) (Ugandan Ministry of Education and Sports 2008). By contrast, enrolment had increased by only 0.9 million between 1986 and 1997. In 2003, the national gross primary school enrolment ratio exceeded 100 per cent (at 127 per cent) (ODI 2005), indicating that children beyond the standard primary school age had resumed their enrolment in primary school due to UPE. Attendance increased from 62.1 per cent in 1992 to 83.6 per cent in 1999 (Deininger 2003). Grogan (2008) confirms this finding of significantly increased school attendance due to UPE across various socioeconomic groups, via a regression discontinuity design study.

Caveats associated with UPE

Despite the success of the UPE and capitation grant policy, there are several caveats that have been highlighted by researchers. These observations provide insight into how the effectiveness of this type of policy could be further enhanced.

Free education appears not to have worked well for poor families living in rural areas. Ssewamala et al. (2011) suggest that simply providing free education was not attractive enough for these families. The infrastructure in rural schools was not adequate to accommodate an increasing number of students. It also appears that poor families preferred to keep their children at home to minimise other costs associated with schooling, such as uniforms and food. Given that post-primary education was still not free, UPE may not have provided enough of an incentive for poor families to send children to primary school.

There was likely some leakage of public funds via corruption among local governmental officials, lack of knowledge and inefficient information transfer to the general public (Bjorkman 2004). Usage of capitation grants was not clearly monitored; low accountability and monitoring of funds facilitated misuse and bribes. As a result, many schools were unaware of their entitlement to additional funding. Misuse of public funds was already known to be a problem in Uganda; Reinikka and Svensson (2004) find that in the pre-UPE period between 1991 and 1995, only 13 per cent of funds provided by the central government in the form of capitation grants reached schools. As a result, around the time of the introduction of UPE, the Ugandan government introduced a program to combat corruption by publishing information in newspapers about the timing and amount of funds disbursed to districts as capitation grants. Bjorkman finds that this program was effective, although effectiveness varied between districts, primarily due to discrepancies in newspaper penetration. Students in districts highly exposed to the information campaign scored 0.40 standard deviations better in the Primary Leaving Examination (PLE) than those that were less exposed.

Classroom overcrowding also occurred (Nishimura et al. 2009), and it is possible that the quality of education suffered as a result (Sawamura 2008). The evidence on the effects of class size on education is relatively mixed in general, but O'Sullivan (2006) presents Uganda as a particular example where smaller classes have seemed to result in increased education quality. The benefits of UPE could be further enhanced by mitigating this potential problem. However, it should be noted that the phenomenon of classroom overcrowding due to UPE reflects an

increase in demand for education, which is a positive outcome and shows that the program worked.

There are several possible reasons why schools were unable to keep up with the rapid increase in demand for education, including a lack of financial resources and a shortage of classrooms (O'Sullivan 2006, Nishimura et al. 2009). The most obvious way to deal with these problems is additional government investment in response to the wide take-up of the program. In general, teacher shortages may also be caused by an inflexible labour market and the effects of regulation about who is allowed to teach, although the extent to which these factors were influential here is uncertain. O'Sullivan notes that lower primary classes in Uganda have tended to be larger than upper primary classes, which the author believes is due to two main reasons: the higher dropout of students in UPE (as discussed in the next paragraph); and the use of subject-specific teachers in upper primary, which requires more teachers when compared to class-level teaching, where each teacher may teach all subjects. On the latter point, this is a school-level tendency that actually goes against Ugandan government policy, which dictates that all grades should have class teaching. O'Sullivan suggests that if this existing policy were better implemented, it could both reduce the dropout rate at lower primary grades and reduce class size across the board.

We make two final points. Some researchers have pointed to an increased dropout rate for students enrolled in level seven as a negative effect of the policy (e.g. ODI 2005). This was probably partly because primary education had been made free, but post-primary education had not. However, it is likely that this was not really a negative effect. If the extra students that dropped out were largely a subset of those students who had been driven to take up education by the policy, we would still see this as a successful outcome. It does not appear to be known whether dropout rates increased among this group. The important point is that the new policy almost certainly resulted in students taking up education who would not have done so in the absence of the policy. Additionally, some negative effects on academic achievement were observed during the evaluation period. On average, PLE scores across districts declined from 10.4 to 10.1 points between 1996 and 2002 (Bjorkman 2004). Again, this decline is to be expected due to the broader take-up of education. It is unknown whether PLE scores reduced for those students who would have been enrolled in level six regardless of the policy, which is the important question for policy evaluation. While academic results were not improved on average, it is misleading to conclude that student outcomes were reduced in aggregate or that the total welfare of students suffered as a result of providing free primary education.

Conclusion

In this chapter, we have seen that education reforms undertaken in developing countries can result in broadly successful outcomes. Uganda's UPE and capitation grant policy resulted in increased enrolment and attendance, despite a negative effect on average test scores, which was expected, and Argentina's policy of school decentralisation resulted in improved test scores. On the other hand, the main problem in both cases, especially Argentina, was that the benefits of the policy did not extend well enough to more disadvantaged students. We have also noted some further promising policy ideas in developing countries, including giving parents more information about school quality and returns to schooling, and providing education in a way that addresses students' individual learning needs.

The effectiveness of a policy can vary considerably depending on its context, as well as the details of policy design and implementation. In developing countries, systemic vulnerabilities such as poverty, attitudes towards educating girls, weak governance and lack of infrastructure

and other public resources may present challenges for policymakers. This suggests that other policy responses to tackle these issues in parallel could positively influence the response to an education intervention. A successful example is the Ugandan policy to combat corruption in the disbursement of funds to schools by publicising information about funding by district. This resulted in increased test scores for the students who were exposed to this information. These ideas may be less relevant for policy to improve student outcomes in developed countries, which we explore in the next chapter.

Chapter 6: What policies have been proposed to improve student outcomes in developed countries, and how effective have they been?

There has been an increasing focus in developed countries on lifting educational standards (OECD 2010). Reasons for this include recognition of the positive externalities of education and demand for higher literacy and numeracy skills. The success of these policies in improving student outcomes has been widely debated, similar to developing countries as we saw in Chapter 5. This chapter examines two particularly prominent types of policies: programs that create incentives for teachers, and school-level accountability programs that create incentives for school administration and executives.

We focus on the US System for Teacher and Student Advancement and the No Child Left Behind (NCLB) school accountability policy and explore how these approaches have attempted to improve student outcomes. We discuss the evidence on their effectiveness based on quantitative impact evaluations and compare this evidence with other research from outside the US. We then discuss the implications of this evidence for policy development. Our finding is that the evidence on both policies is mixed, and even where a positive impact on student outcomes has been found, there have been negative unintended consequences for some students that undermine the policy intent. This suggests that specific aspects of the policy design need to be altered, or that different policies may need to be implemented to improve outcomes for different sub-groups of students. We finally explore some further policy directions that are supported by positive evidence.

As emphasised in Chapter 5, different policies seem to have different effects depending on the environment. For example, teacher incentive programs appear to have worked better in the UK and Israel than in the US. While it is useful to assess what has and has not worked in other contexts, the best practice approach is to base policy recommendations as much as possible on evidence from the policymaker's own environment.

Teacher incentives

In this section, we discuss merit-based pay programs – that is, policies that offer financial rewards to teachers based on their students' academic outcomes, evidenced by standardised test scores. Merit-based pay programs have not been widely taken up, partly due to the risk of perverse incentives, such as teachers "teaching to the test" or encouraging cheating, and also possibly due to opposition from teachers' unions (Jacob & Ludwig 2008; Donnelly 2015, p. 634). Nevertheless, education policymakers worldwide continue to show interest in the positive results that teacher incentive programs can provide (Springer et al. 2012, p. 367; Imberman 2015, pp. 1-2; Jacob & Ludwig 2008; Fryer, Levitt, List & Sadoff 2018, p. 4).

The quality of teachers is evidently an important factor in the success of an education system. But how can we measure teacher quality and how much does it matter for student outcomes? Chetty, Friedman and Rockoff (2014) investigate the relationship between 'teacher value-added' and longer-term measures of student outcomes. They calculate teacher value-added based on teachers' impacts on students' test scores, using data sourced from a large, unspecified school district and tax records for over 1 million children in the US. The authors find a strong relationship – students assigned to teachers with a high value-added score are more likely to attend college and earn higher salaries. For example, replacing a teacher in the bottom 5 per cent of value-added with an average teacher would increase the present value of students' lifetime income by around \$250,000 per classroom. These findings demonstrate why

policymakers might be interested in focusing on teacher quality. However, the authors note that such policies can carry the risk of perverse incentives as mentioned in the previous paragraph.

The US System for Teacher and Student Advancement

The System for Teacher and Student Advancement, formerly the Teacher Advancement Program (TAP), is a nationwide teacher effectiveness program in the US, and was designed on the basis of merit-based pay (IES 2015, p. 1). Several empirical studies have been conducted on the effectiveness of the program in selected locations throughout the US. A summary of the findings of these studies is presented in Table 3. These studies have shown mixed results, with no significant impact on student outcomes except where the incentives were very large (Fryer et al. 2018, pp. 6-9; Imberman 2015, p. 6).

Table 3: Summary of studies evaluating the US System for Teacher and Student Advancement (Fryer et al. 2018)

Location and study	Research design	Incentives	Findings
Chicago: An evaluation of the TAP in its first year (Glazerman, McKie & Carey 2009).	16 K-8 public schools volunteered to participate. Eight randomly assigned to receive TAP program in first year; the remaining eight in following year.	Teachers received an expected annual bonus of \$2,000 based on their value added and classroom observations. Teachers could earn additional pay by being promoted to being a Mentor (\$7,000) or Lead Teacher (\$15,000).	First year of the program increased teacher retention but no impact on teacher satisfaction or student achievement.
Metropolitan Nashville: Evaluation of a three-year pilot initiative based on teacher incentives between 2006-07 and 2008-09 school years (Springer et al. 2010)	Around 300 middle school mathematics teachers volunteered to participate and were randomly assigned to a treatment or control group.	Educators in the treatment group could earn up to \$15,000 as a bonus if their students performed at least as well as the level achieved by the top 5 per cent of teachers in the district; \$5,000 and \$10,000 for exceeding the 80th and the 90th percentiles respectively.	No significant treatment effect on student achievement.

<p>New York City: An experiment on teacher incentives (Fryer 2013)</p>	<p>Quasi-experiment conducted in over 200 public schools.</p>	<p>Each participating school was eligible to earn \$3,000 for every union-represented staff member, for the school to distribute at its own discretion, if the school met an annual performance target as set by the Department of Education and based on school report card scores. Schools were given \$1,500 per union staff member if they met at least 75% of the target.</p>	<p>No significant effect on student achievement or teacher behaviour. Possibly a small negative effect for larger schools where free-riding may have been problematic.</p>
<p>Texas: An experiment to evaluate the ‘Team Pay for Performance’ group incentive (Springer et al. 2012).</p>	<p>Over two years, study included 159 randomly assigned teams of teachers, teaching core subjects to students in grades six to eight in nine middle schools.</p>	<p>The Team Pay for Performance program awarded teams of middle school teachers bonuses based on their collective contribution to students’ test score gains.</p>	<p>No significant impact on academic achievement of students.</p>
<p>10 school districts in the US: Evaluation of the Teacher Incentive Fund on the implementation and impacts of pay-for-performance across four years (Chiang et al. 2017)</p>	<p>Schools assigned randomly. 65 schools in treatment group; 66 in control group.</p>	<p>Pay-for-performance bonus payments based on educator and student outcomes.</p>	<p>Estimated impact of incentives on student test scores was small, ranging from 0.02 to 0.06 standard deviations in mathematics and 0.03 to 0.04 standard deviations in reading.</p>

In light of what we know about the very large impacts of teacher quality on student outcomes (Chetty et al. 2014), the above findings suggest that the best policies may involve recruiting high quality teachers and having the ability to dismiss poor quality ones. This requires broadly agreed upon measures of teacher quality and a more flexible approach by unions. There may be other measures of teacher quality besides value-added, such as measures based on principal evaluations or classroom observation. Chetty et al. propose that these types of measures could be analysed for their effects on student outcomes in a similar way to their study on value-added.

Evidence beyond the US

Empirical studies from other countries suggest a potentially more positive effect from teacher incentive programs relative to what we have seen in the US. For example, studies on student performance-related pay have shown a positive impact on student performance in the UK and Israel (Woessmann 2008, pp. 210-211). Sclafani (2010, pp. 40-42) similarly demonstrates positive effects on student achievement in external examinations in Israel, as well as in developing nations such as Kenya and India.

In Singapore, the Ministry of Education (2019) provides several incentives for teachers. Teachers are paid a relatively high base salary and are awarded end-of-year performance bonuses of up to three months' salary. These bonuses are allocated based on performance reviews, which involve considerations about student achievement (Sclafani 2010, p. 40). The intention is to attract higher quality teachers to the profession (Ginsburg, Leinwand, Anstrom & Pollock 2005). Student performance in Singapore is consistently very high, especially in mathematics. Singapore scored among the top three countries in the 2012 and 2019 Program for International Student Assessment tests, and outperformed all other countries in 2015 (OECD 2018d). Therefore, it appears that Singapore's approach to education is inducing favourable student outcomes. However, we cannot on the basis of the above purely correlational evidence conclusively say that Singapore's targeted financial incentives for teachers have led to higher student outcomes. For example, higher salaries may have contributed more to teacher quality than performance bonuses.

In summary, evidence on teacher incentives is again mixed and appears to have worked in some places better than others. There may be other initiatives that would work better than teacher incentive programs with fewer adverse side effects. Clearly, many education systems could benefit from an increased focus on teacher quality in relation to decisions about teacher recruitment, management and pay.

School accountability policies

School accountability policies aim to improve educational outcomes by incentivising schools to lift their standards. There are three typical elements that these policies may be comprised of: standardised state-wide testing, public reporting of performance results and explicit performance-based rewards and sanctions (Figlio & Loeb 2011). Standardised testing and results reports can provide parents and community members with comparative information about how well schools are doing. Poorly performing schools are incentivised to improve via the implicit threat of parents being able to move their children to better performing schools, and potentially by the threat of explicit government sanctions (Figlio & Loeb 2011, p. 389).

The US No Child Left Behind Act

The No Child Left Behind Act was passed by the Bush administration in January 2002. The policy's aims were for all students to achieve proficiency in reading and mathematics by 2013-14, and to close the achievement gap between the highest and the lowest performing American students (Hursh 2007; Dee & Jacob 2011, p. 420). The policy introduced annual standardised testing of students. It compelled states to publicly report school performance ratings, set performance benchmarks for schools, and introduce explicit sanctions for persistently poorly performing schools. Schools that repeatedly failed to meet progress benchmarks faced federally enforced sanctions such as provisions for students to attend alternative schools and staff replacements, as well as restructuring and eventual closure (Dee & Jacob 2011, p. 420). NCLB thus involved both implicit and explicit sanctions for poorly performing schools, which economic theory suggests should provide strong incentives to

improve performance results. Several researchers have addressed this question empirically, outlined as follows.

Measured impact of NCLB

Studies into NCLB's impact have generally been faced with the common problem of the missing counterfactual: the Act applied to all American public schools, and it was not practically possible for researchers to randomly assign schools to treatment or control groups. Therefore, most of the impact evaluations of NCLB have conducted their analysis via quasi- or natural experiments. These have shown mixed to positive results.

Some states had already implemented school accountability policies before NCLB was introduced. This created a quasi-experiment where the schools that were affected by NCLB were the treatment group and the schools that were much less affected due to pre-existing state policies were the comparison group. Dee and Jacob (2011) investigate this quasi-experiment, finding that NCLB resulted in substantial improvements in grade four and grade eight mathematics by 2007 (in particular, 0.23 of a standard deviation improvement in grade four mathematics), but no statistically significant improvements in reading or in terms of closing proficiency gaps in numeracy and literacy. Moreover, despite the improvement in mathematics, 60 per cent of fourth graders still failed to achieve proficiency benchmarks by 2007 (Dee & Jacob 2011, p. 442).

Given that NCLB only applied to public schools, a quasi-experiment arises with private schools as the comparison group. Investigating the policy from this perspective, Wong, Cook and Steiner (2010) find similar results – significant improvements in grade four and grade eight mathematics in addition to improvements in reading within states that demanded especially high proficiency standards and imposed additional sanctions on top of those of NCLB. These results suggest that explicit sanctions may have been an important contributor to some of the positive outcomes from the program.

The positive impacts of NCLB were not limited to academic achievement. An analysis of survey data by Reback, Rockoff and Schwartz (2014, p. 231) suggests that test-focused instruction under NCLB improved students' enjoyment of learning and reduced exam-related anxiety.

Unintended consequences

Despite some positive impacts, NCLB has been criticised for having negative unintended consequences. Several studies find that schools narrowed their syllabi in response to the focus areas of the policy, reducing instruction time in science, social sciences and the arts (Reback et al. 2014, Pederson 2007, Grey 2009). The provisions of the Act also seemed to incentivise schools to expel students or hold them back in order to improve school performance. For example, King Middle School's average scores increased from the 70th to the 72nd percentile between 2002 and 2003 – however, no student at the school improved their marks during this period; the major change was the unenrolment of a single student (Darling-Hammond 2007a). This was the case for many schools across the US, where students who did poorly, even including special needs students, were increasingly likely to be excluded, transferred or expelled in order to improve the school's performance (Darling-Hammond 2007b).

Of course, penalising underperforming students, as well as reducing the focus of education on subjects that were not measured by NCLB, undermines the intended effect of 'No Child Left Behind'. Community concerns regarding these unintended consequences, along with growing discontent among state public school systems (Pinder 2010, p. 29), ultimately led to the end of NCLB. In 2015, the system was repealed and replaced by the Every Student Succeeds Act,

which handed more control over to the states in terms of school accountability (Heise 2017, p. 1872).

Evidence beyond the US

Several studies have been conducted on policies similar to NCLB in other developed countries. Centralised reporting of school performance results and associated sanctions were introduced in the UK in 1988 (Burgess, Propper, Slater & Wilson 2005; West 2010). Wales opted out of this system in 2001, whereas England maintained it. This created a natural experiment which could be used to assess the policy's effectiveness. Using this design, Burgess, Wilson and Worth (2013, p. 58) find a resulting sharp decline in test scores in Wales by 1.78 General Certificate of Secondary Education points per student per year (roughly 0.21 of a standard deviation). This suggests a positive effect on student outcomes from these accountability policies. On the other hand, studies on accountability policies that do not include explicit sanctions, such as has been the case in Australia, have tended to show weaker incentives for schools to improve (Coelli, Foster & Leigh 2018).

As with the US, there have been unintended consequences associated with the UK model. Burgess et al. (2005) find that the lowest performing students (as well as the highest performing students) suffered lower grades as a result of schools focusing their resources on students that were on the margin of passing. This again emphasises the point that accountability policies do not always have the effect that governments intend or expect from introducing them. In the case of the UK, the effects of the policy on economic efficiency or even equity are not entirely clear. However, it is clear that school accountability policies have not always worked well in lifting outcomes for the most poorly performing students, even if they may lift average outcomes.

Further promising directions for policy

So far, we have seen mixed results from teacher incentive and school accountability programs. Assessing what might work better is an active area of research. We now briefly outline some policy directions which have shown more promise. In Jacob and Ludwig's (2008) extensive review of the evidence, they propose the following four areas for education policy to improve student outcomes among poor children and productively enhance the American education system: increasing investment in early childhood education, improving school accountability policies, increasing the emphasis on evidence-based teaching practices and ensuring that there is sufficient choice of schools available to families.

Firstly, there is evidence that investment in early childhood education improves a variety of outcomes in the longer-term, such as educational attainment. One example of this type of policy is Head Start. As we saw in Chapter 4 (also see IES 2021), Head Start is a long-running intervention designed to provide resources and support to low-income children at the Pre-kindergarten level, which has been shown to result in improved academic and longer-term life outcomes for the students involved in the program.

Secondly, the effects of school accountability policies are highly dependent on the specific design of the policy. At the time of Jacob and Ludwig's (2008) review, NCLB was still active. Although we have seen that there were mixed impacts from NCLB, the authors recommend keeping such a policy but revising it. This could include: adopting common achievement standards across states, focusing accountability on student growth rather than proficiency levels, providing states and districts with the flexibility to focus limited resources on the most disadvantaged schools, and reconciling federal and state accountability systems.

Thirdly, schools could be incentivised to adopt teaching practices which have been proven to work on the basis of rigorous evidence – such as Success for All, which is a whole-school reform focusing on prevention and early intervention of literacy difficulties. The government could focus R&D spending towards similar research. Generally, Jacob and Ludwig (2008) advocate for more evidence-based practice in education policy. They suggest on this basis that allowing alternative certification routes into teaching might help increase the supply of teachers into disadvantaged schools. An example of a program that facilitates this is Teach for America (IES 2021), which enables high need public schools to be staffed with non-traditionally trained teachers, and has been shown to result in improved student proficiency in mathematics and science. The IES outlines a range of additional American programs which involve specific types of curricula or teaching methods and are supported by empirical evidence, especially starting at the Pre-kindergarten or Kindergarten stage, such as Literacy Express and Peer-Assisted Learning Strategies.

Finally, Jacob and Ludwig (2008) recommend maintaining and possibly increasing the range of public school options that parents and children can choose from at the local level. The authors acknowledge that further research is required in this area. Somewhat relevant is the evidence in support of American programs that involve networks of public charter schools, including the Knowledge is Power Program and Green Dot Public Schools, which have been demonstrated to have favourable effects on the academic development of disadvantaged children (IES 2021).

Conclusion

In this chapter, we have examined teacher and school incentive programs to improve student outcomes. Impact evaluations of the US System for Teacher and Student Advancement have shown mixed results. The NCLB school accountability program has been associated with somewhat more positive effects on academic results in some subjects, especially mathematics. However, there has also been evidence of concerning negative effects, such as students exhibiting poor academic performance being excluded, transferred or expelled to ensure that schools technically met their own performance targets. We have touched on some further promising areas for policy: increasing investment in early childhood education, revising the design of school accountability policies to correct unwanted effects, promoting evidence-based teaching practices in general and ensuring that families have sufficiently many school options.

In developed countries, the potential adverse side effects of education policies are less likely to be a result of institutional weaknesses (as in the developing countries case), and more likely due to aspects of policy design that contribute to a particular incentive structure. It is important that policymakers consider how the evidence applies to their specific context. In the next chapter, we turn our focus towards policies to improve student outcomes in Australia.

Chapter 7: Education policy and student outcomes in Australia

Since 2000, student outcomes in Australia as measured by standardised test scores have been declining in key subjects, such as mathematics, science and reading. This suggests that the ability of schools to prepare students to excel in adult life may be diminishing. There is also a social equity issue: learning outcomes are significantly worse for students from disadvantaged backgrounds, such as those with low socioeconomic status or of Indigenous background.

In this chapter, we first examine the evidence on Australian student outcomes in more detail. We then discuss education policy to lift student outcomes in terms of four main themes: ensuring that students obtain skills required by the evolving employment market; improving access to early childhood education; improving school accountability; and addressing equity issues. We explore some of the main policies that are currently in place, policy alternatives and what the evidence points to.

There are very few Australian education policy impact evaluation studies, which naturally imposes limitations on our understanding of what policies do and do not work. This is primarily due to a lack of data relative to other developed countries. Data to evaluate education policy in Australia exist, but both state and federal education agencies tend to be hesitant about sharing data with researchers and do not always fully cooperate with each other. Evidence on policy effectiveness has been drawn from a wide array of observational and experimental studies on specific elements of policy and program design.

Trends in student outcomes

In this section, we summarise recent trends in Australian student outcomes, under the international frameworks of PISA, TIMSS and PIRLS. We also cover the Australia-specific frameworks of NAPLAN and the National Sample Assessment for Information and Communication Technology Literacy (NAP-ICTL). Overall, Australia's international ranking has dropped and the data indicate relatively stagnant performance over recent years, despite some positive findings for particular year groups or demographics.

The PISA framework assesses the performance of 15 year old students across various focus subjects. In 2018, Australian students fell below the OECD average for the first time in terms of performance in mathematics. While performance has also been falling in reading and science, Australia still exceeds the OECD average in these categories. Between 2000 and 2018, Australia's world ranking dropped from 4th to 16th in reading literacy, 7th to 29th in mathematics, and 4th to 17th in science literacy (ACER 2019). Between 2000 and 2015, the size of the gap between Australian student outcomes and student outcomes in the other countries that were in the top five in 2000 doubled in mathematics and science (ACER 2017a). PISA results also show that students from the Northern Territory and Tasmania perform on average worse than the other states of Australia in reading literacy and science. In mathematics, student performance in Tasmania ranks the lowest compared to all other states (ACER 2017a).

One of the causes behind this observed poorer performance of 15 year old students when compared internationally is the variation between advantaged and less advantaged students. The difference in PISA results in 2015 between Australian students from advantaged and disadvantaged backgrounds was equivalent to three years of schooling or one full proficiency level, which was higher than in other OECD countries (ACER 2017a). Australia is considered to have a relatively high quality of education but low equity when compared to other OECD countries (Baroutsis & Lingard 2014, p. 433).

Changes in Australia's TIMSS and PIRLS results over time tell a more mixed story when compared to the PISA rankings. The TIMSS framework assesses fourth and eighth grade students in terms of performance in mathematics and science. The results between 2007 and 2015 show essentially no improvement among year four students in either category. For year eight students, TIMSS results did not improve between 2011 and 2015 (ACER 2016). On the other hand, average performance did increase in all categories but year four mathematics between 2015 and 2019 (ACER 2020). The PIRLS framework assesses reading literacy among fourth grade students. Australian year four students have recently demonstrated a significant gain in terms of PIRLS results (reading literacy), with a 17 point gain between 2011 and 2016 (ACER 2017b).

NAPLAN is an annual assessment for students in Australia in years three, five, seven and nine that covers reading, writing, language conventions (spelling, grammar and punctuation) and numeracy. In 2018, NAPLAN participation rates exceeded 90 per cent for all of these domains apart from year nine numeracy, which fell just below this level. Some results describing performance between 2008, when the program was introduced, and 2018, are as follows – and the story is again mixed. Year three and year five reading have improved (both in terms of mean and proportion of students attaining the national minimum standard) – and this is also the case just among Indigenous students. However, performance in writing has declined (since 2011, which is the base year for this component of the framework) for years five, seven and nine. Numeracy achievement has remained unchanged for years three and seven since 2008, but increased for years five and nine (ACARA 2018).

NAP-ICTL was launched in 2005. It is conducted every three years to assess students of years six and 10 on the basis of ICT skills. Results in 2017 are not significantly better than the results from 2011 or 2008 for both years of students assessed (ACARA 2017, pp. 97-98).

Despite some of these relatively neutral results at the domestic level, Goss (2016) indicates that Australia's falling international standards are concerning. Our reading performance in PISA has declined by the equivalent of around six months' worth of learning since 2000, in contrast to substantial improvements in other countries. Gaps between stronger and weaker students are widening. Otherwise similar students from families with limited education are falling up to two years behind their peers between years three and nine. Approximately one out of four students do not finish year 12 by age 19, and many of these will leave school without appropriate capabilities in reading and mathematics. Even our strongest students are not internationally competitive enough – only 15 per cent reach the highest levels of mathematical proficiency in PISA, compared to 40 per cent in the five best systems worldwide. Goss suggests that the weaknesses of the Australian education system may have potentially serious consequences for future productivity, innovation and economic growth.

The ability of the education system to prepare students for the future

The Melbourne Declaration, established by state and federal governments in 2009 and replaced in 2019 by the updated Mparntwe Declaration, provided a set of guiding principles for education policy, practice and delivery in Australia (Carter 2018). It intended among other things to “support the senior years of schooling and the provision of high-quality pathways to facilitate effective transitions between further study, training and employment” (ACARA 2017, p. 99). More broadly, the goals of the Melbourne Declaration, which are almost identical to their revised versions in the new Declaration, were: that Australian schooling promotes equity and excellence, and that all young Australians become successful learners, confident and creative individuals, and active and informed citizens.

The Melbourne Declaration was accompanied by a four-year action plan for the states and territories, but its goals were set up as broad intentions rather than quantifiable targets. This makes it difficult to assess what it achieved. However, the issues with academic performance and equity in Australia in recent years, as mentioned earlier and also highlighted by Gonski et al. (2018), suggest that the goals of the Declaration have not been achieved. This may be in part due to its abstractness. Choi (2019) and Carter (2018) also propose that it was ineffective due to a lack of focus on adapting learning practices to a rapidly changing world and workforce, which includes aspects such as the growth of non-routine occupations, information saturation and “fake news”.

Education policy should ensure that students obtain skills that prepare them for future employment or higher education in a complex and rapidly changing world (Gonski et al. 2018). The workforce is changing, with PwC (2017) suggesting that 44 per cent of current jobs will be disrupted due to technology over the next 20 years. In 2019, the state and federal governments jointly released ‘Future Ready: A student-focused National Career Education Strategy’, which is a high level outline of six objectives for an education system that is well adapted to the needs of the future. These objectives are largely centred around building transferable skills, equity in career preparation, partnerships between all stakeholders and evidence-based education practices. This strategy indicates an understanding in government of the importance of future preparedness in education. It remains to be seen whether the approach to building such principles into our education system is still too loosely defined.

There are few empirical studies in Australia which are relevant to this question of making the education system adaptable to the needs of the future. However, Australian studies have found that encouraging transitions to higher levels of education results in positive outcomes over a person’s lifetime. Powdthavee, Lekfuangfu & Wooden (2015) find that a higher number of years spent on education is associated with higher levels of life satisfaction among adults, in terms of employment, income, marriage, children and health. Daly, Lewis, Corliss & Heaslip (2015) have found significantly higher returns to a Bachelor’s degree than to a year 12 certificate only, and that the private return to university education is especially high for Bachelor’s degrees in dentistry, medicine and information technology. It is a positive sign that enrolment rates for higher education in Australia have been increasing, reaching the highest level in 2016 with 41 per cent of 19 year olds enrolled in higher education institutions compared to less than 30 percent in 2006 (Norton & Cherastidtham 2018). Policies that motivate more students to seek higher levels of education may result in improved future outcomes.

Challenges with STEM education

As indicated earlier, student results in science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) subjects have been stagnating or declining over recent years, and there has been a decline in students studying mathematics at an advanced level (ACER 2017a). In response, the Australian government has shown a particular interest in STEM subjects, with the rationale that this will help students to be better prepared for the jobs of the future (Education Council 2015). For example, in 2020, the government introduced changes in university degree funding, such that the cost of studying STEM subjects was significantly reduced (by up to 62 per cent) and the cost of other subjects such as in the arts was significantly increased (by up to 113 per cent) (Tehan 2020).

In 2015, the government released the National STEM School Education Strategy 2016-2026, a broad nationwide roadmap with the aim of addressing low achievement in STEM (Education Council 2015). Murphy, MacDonald, Danaia and Wang (2019) critically analyse this strategy

and Australia's approach to STEM education. The results from their report are mixed. The authors reflect that an increased focus on STEM education is positive, and that Australia's approach takes into account some of the themes in the literature related to effective STEM education, such as incorporating better STEM learning practices and building teacher capacity. However, they are concerned that the government has not sufficiently considered the challenges of STEM dispositions, equity and transitions within and between educational sectors. They also argue that STEM thinking has not been incorporated well enough into early childhood education.

An Education Council (2019) report provides a wide-ranging overview of 69 initiatives on education in STEM at the national, state and school level, and a summary of external evaluation studies for 16 of them. These initiatives include academic partnerships, scholarships, and teacher education and development programs. The findings of this report are again mixed but overall positive regarding student outcomes and effects on abilities of teachers. Some of the more successful interventions have included: Thinking Maths (South Australia), a professional development program to deepen subject matter and pedagogical knowledge for mathematics teachers between years six and nine; the STEM Learning Project (Western Australia) which is a program to support the integrated teaching of STEM by providing resources to teachers in consultation with them such as through workshops; and Teacher Development Schools (Western Australia) which facilitates sharing of expertise in STEM teaching practices among teachers in a practical, school-based environment. The report notes that more time is needed to provide a more comprehensive picture of the impacts of recent developments in STEM education policy in Australia. The report also acknowledges a limitation in its own findings that an assessment of the quality of each of the evaluation studies has not been conducted.

Despite an increasing focus on the importance of STEM education in Australia, there is a level of confusion about how pervasive the need for STEM will be in the future labour market. Some commentators such as Segal (2016) and Finkel (2016) have argued that the supply of STEM graduates is too low to meet expectations of future demand. On the other hand, Norton (2016) has contended that government policy and rhetoric have created an oversupply, and that many STEM graduates are struggling to find jobs, especially in their chosen field. Although the skills shortages in industry are real, they seem to exist in some STEM fields but not others. And American research from Deming (2017) has empirically demonstrated an increasing focus on social skills rather than STEM skills in the labour market, as these will continue to be very hard to automate. For example, between 1980 and 2012, jobs requiring high levels of social interaction grew by around 12 percentage points as a share of the US labour force, whereas mathematics-intensive but less social jobs shrank by 3.3 percentage points.

At the same time, there is some international evidence that STEM education is associated with better future outcomes for students. For example, recent research by Dahl, Rooth and Stenberg (2020) indicates that high school majors taken up by Swedish students at the end of ninth grade go on to affect their earnings as adults. Their study uses a regression discontinuity design on school register data from 1977-1991 linked to data on individuals' earnings as adults. The authors find that engineering, natural science and business yield higher earnings, whereas social science and humanities result in a substantial relative reduction in earnings. The discrepancy between these fields in terms of future returns may be as large as the equivalent of two years of additional education. The differences in adult earnings may largely be attributed to differences in occupation and college major, which flow on from the decisions students have made at age 16.

Overall, it appears that STEM skills are increasingly important in the workforce, and thus a focus on providing students with these skills is justified, but much more nuance is required in our understanding of this trend and the consequent policy response. Some areas of knowledge in STEM, such as life science, are not highly sought after. It seems likely that many students could gain a requisite understanding of STEM skills or ways of thinking without having to do a full university degree in a STEM area. It could also be harmful to the labour market to strongly encourage a large number of students to study in fields that they might have little aptitude for or interest in. There is the obvious point that no one knows what the future will look like, and statements about the future job market are not usually framed with this ambiguity. Australian researchers such as Panizzon, Corrigan, Forgasz and Hopkins (2015) have called for more clarity from government and industry on where the real gaps exist in the Australian STEM workforce. This requires better employment data, analysis of that data and communication of the resulting messages to prospective students.

[Access to early childhood education](#)

Another area of focus for the Australian government over the past decade has been improving the provision of preschool to children from all socioeconomic backgrounds. Early childhood education and care is the fastest growing component of Australia's education system in terms of expenditure (Hurley, Noble & Jackson 2020). In 2008, the government introduced the first National Partnership Agreement on Universal Access to Early Childhood Education (of several since then), which is a Commonwealth funding agreement to support states and territories in increasing participation rates in preschool and ensuring national consistency in the number of hours available (DESE 2021). The government's most recent National Report on the Partnership Agreements reflects steady improvements in preschool participation since 2008 (DESE 2018). On the other hand, in 2018, 30 per cent of Australian children still did not attend 15 hours of preschool per week, increasing to 35 per cent for vulnerable and disadvantaged children and 41 per cent for Indigenous children (AEDC 2018).

One criticism of funding arrangements to do with early childhood education has been that they are unstable, being renewed annually via these National Partnership Agreements. Hurley et al. (2020) have suggested that certainty around the future of funding, as is the case in other education sectors, might give parents more confidence about availability of care, and might assist with attracting higher quality staff to the sector. The authors also argue that current arrangements are complex and therefore obscure how much governments are spending on each student. This makes it more difficult for researchers to assess how the sector is functioning.

The government's policy focus on early childhood education is supported by Australian evidence. Experimental and observational studies have found that attending preschool has a positive effect on test scores in early school years (Warren & Haisken-DeNew 2013, Claessens & Garrett 2014). Moreover, preschool teachers with higher levels of education (degree or diploma) provide higher levels of advantage to students in these early years of schooling (Warren & Haisken-DeNew 2013), indicating the importance of investment in the education of teachers who are involved in early childhood education.

[Improving school accountability](#)

In 2010, the Australian government launched an initiative to make student assessment data from NAPLAN results for all schools available to the general public on the MySchool website. The primary purpose of this intervention was to increase public scrutiny of school

performance, which was hoped to result in improved school management and student learning. The policy has received considerable negative attention and there has been a significant body of Australian literature about the unintended negative consequences of school accountability reforms based on students' test results. These consequences include: teachers neglecting to teach non-tested parts of the curriculum, schools participating in perverse practices to improve test scores, a high level of pressure on individual students to perform better on tests, growth of the testing industry driven by commercial interests, and unrealistic assumptions on the causal link between testing and learning (for example, see: APPA 2009; Wu 2010; Klenowski & Wyatt-Smith 2012; Thompson & Harbaugh 2013; Polesel, Rice, & Dulfer 2014; Johnston 2017). This is in addition to the international literature and our discussion of some of these issues in the previous chapter.

There is a dearth of policy impact evaluation studies pertaining to the MySchool initiative. One experimental design shows that there was no meaningful change in policies and practices in low performing schools (as reported by principals) after the publication of NAPLAN results on the MySchool website (Coelli et al. 2018). However, the authors do acknowledge some concerns regarding sample selection bias in their study.

Teacher and school performance, and consequently student outcomes, might be better improved by policies that improve the teacher qualification process and ensure that teachers are incentivised appropriately. Mayer et al. (2015) find that teachers with a Master's or Bachelor's degree perceive themselves to be more effective than teachers with a Graduate Diploma. The same study finds teachers also perceive that a relevant practicum during their teacher education period prepares them better for their career and makes them more effective (Mayer et al. 2015). Also, while Australia offers slightly better wages for teachers compared to other countries, wages tend to peak after seven years (OECD 2019). This may encourage them to move into management roles instead of continuing to teach. Teachers' wages do not compare well to other professional fields, which disincentivises young people from becoming teachers. As we saw in the previous chapter, an increased focus on teacher quality in relation to decisions about teacher recruitment, management and pay could yield a higher quality of teaching and consequently better student outcomes.

There are further ways to facilitate the improvement of teaching practices. Australian teachers spend more time in the classroom than teachers in other countries (OECD 2018e). It is tempting to interpret this result as evidence that the issue of declining student outcomes is related to quality rather than quantity of education – as clearly quantity is not an issue. While this is probably the case, a strongly related issue is that when teachers have less time in the classroom, this gives them more time to improve their teaching practices. For example, teachers in Australia have 50 per cent less non-teaching time than in Shanghai, where teachers on average have larger but fewer classes, and spend many non-teaching hours each week on other important activities such as observation, collaboration and research, which can contribute towards much improved quality of teaching (Goss 2016). Similar practices could be adopted in Australia.

Several researchers have drawn attention to the importance of student progress rather than achievement in absolute terms, both in designing school accountability frameworks (Jacob & Ludwig 2008), and in terms of pedagogical practices. In particular, Goss (2016) proposes a system of "targeted teaching", where teachers identify what each student is capable of learning next, teach them accordingly and monitor progress. He highlights Australian and international evidence that this approach helps students learn faster, and would help with narrowing equity gaps. In general, he notes that it is important to look at the evidence on what

works in teaching practices, and that this might provide more effective ways to lift student outcomes than teacher incentive or school accountability policies. This involves not only using the findings of Australian studies and promoting further empirical research, which requires both appropriate research funding and release of data, but also to draw from the latest findings in other countries.

Challenges with equity in student outcomes

Australian studies have found a relationship between test scores and students' environments, which includes their socioeconomic background and parental education, location of school, and sense of belonging to the school (Chua, Khan, Humphry & Hassell 2017; Reynolds, Lee, Turner, Bromhead & Subasic 2017; Miller & Voon 2012). In the 2015 PISA, students from higher socioeconomic backgrounds performed at a significantly higher level than students from lower socioeconomic backgrounds (ACER 2017a). This finding has led to policy interventions focusing on specific populations of disadvantaged students.

One Australian study on an intervention combining instructional and motivational support for students from low-socioeconomic status backgrounds (Ng, Bartlett, Chester & Kersland 2013) shows that two treatment groups showed significantly higher levels of improvements in reading test scores than the control group. One of the treatment groups underwent strategy training in a particular literacy strategy known as 'top-level structuring', and the other group received this training along with an interrelated motivational support component. The improvement in test scores was larger for the latter group, showing that including a motivational support aspect in the intervention made a positive difference.

A survey on adolescent students in Western Australia (Blomfield & Barber 2011) shows that participation in extracurricular activities is associated with improved self-worth and social and academic self-concept. The magnitude of this association is even larger among young people from low socioeconomic status schools; this finding may motivate relevant interventions. Additionally, a quasi-experimental design study among highly disadvantaged schools in Western Sydney (Vaughan & Caldwell 2014) finds that participation in an arts program was associated with improvements in students' scores for socio-emotional wellbeing and the reading component of NAPLAN when compared to students in similar schools that did not offer the arts program. Students who attended the arts program for 12-18 months, compared to students who attended the program for only six months, scored even higher on the NAPLAN test.

Equity considerations are especially relevant for a broader debate about Australia's school funding model. The original Gonski Review on school funding in 2011 proposed that additional funding and a fairer allocation of funding was necessary to improve student outcomes and equity in outcomes (Gonski et al. 2011). At the time of the Review, public schools received \$10,686 per student per year on average in combined state and federal government funding, whereas Catholic schools received \$8286 and independent schools received \$6798 (Hinz 2013). The Review recommended more total funding and that this funding be distributed to government schools, with a minimum standard of funding per student and extra loadings for disadvantaged children. This reform proposal was intended to lift student outcomes, as Australia's decline in results have been due in part to equity problems.

Understanding equity concerns has been made more difficult by the complexity of education funding in Australia. The interactions between state and Commonwealth systems make it challenging for policymakers to assess how funding works on a per school basis. However, in general, state governments largely fund government schools and the federal government

largely funds Catholic and independent schools, despite the states and territories having jurisdiction over most other aspects of education policy. It would simplify the system if federal and state funding responsibilities were more clearly divided. As part of this, funding of schools could be aligned more accurately with the relative disadvantage level of schools (Hinz 2013). The need for coordination of different levels of government means that there have been political obstacles to any significant reform.

Closing the gap for Indigenous students

The proportion of Indigenous children meeting the national minimum standards in NAPLAN in reading and numeracy for years three, four, seven and nine is less than for non-Indigenous children (Department of the Prime Minister and Cabinet 2018). In the 2015 PISA, Indigenous students achieved significantly lower scores than non-Indigenous students in the science, reading and mathematical literacy domains (ACER 2017a).

Government policies to improve NAPLAN scores for Aboriginal and/or Torres Strait Islander students have predominantly focused on improving school attendance. These policies have tended to follow the general direction of the national “closing the gap” strategy (MCEECDYA 2010), and include the MySchool accountability program and a range of other reforms such as the ‘Futures’ initiative in the Northern Territory. Ladwig and Luke (2014) analyse the effectiveness of these policies in terms of NAPLAN performance, using a sample of relevant schools from the MySchool website. The authors’ primary observation is that there is no correlation between any improved attendance resulting from the above policies and student achievement in terms of NAPLAN. The policy recommendation from this is that a focus on attendance is not enough to improve student outcomes – pedagogy and curricula must also be examined and improved where possible.

An earlier study by Luke et al. (2011) evaluates the effects of the Stronger Smarter Learning Communities initiative, which was a project designed to build leadership capacity of school leaders in “hub schools” to act as models for improving Indigenous education. It was intended that this expertise would be transferred to surrounding schools and their leaders through collaboration. The authors similarly find that, despite reported progress in improving school ethos and anecdotally positive effects on Indigenous students, this has not translated into changes in teaching practices, or improvements in attendance or achievement. This indicates negligible progress towards “closing the gap” from the initiative.

Conclusion

Student outcomes in Australia have been on a declining trend in terms of test score measures. Australian federal, state and territory governments have introduced a wide range of strategies and policies over the years with the intention of improving this trend. However, the (albeit limited) evidence shows likely shortfalls in addressing the underlying problems. Our discussion of Australian education policy in this chapter has centred around the themes of: ensuring that students obtain skills required by the evolving employment market; improving access to early childhood education; improving school accountability; and addressing equity issues. While more empirical evidence is required to draw more accurate conclusions, a few key policy directions emerge from our discussion.

Teacher quality is clearly critical. Teacher quality can be improved by implementing better teaching practices based on the domestic and international evidence. One example is “targeted teaching”, in which teachers measure and develop students against their own progress rather than by absolute standards. To refine the teaching process, teachers need to be permitted to spend more time on professional development outside of the classroom.

Again, a focus on student progress rather than absolute performance should be the focus of any school accountability mechanisms, such as MySchool. And from a school management perspective, a focus on teacher quality in hiring and firing decisions is necessary. The effects of remuneration on teacher quality, including whether young people are being properly incentivised to become teachers in the first place, must be understood, as taxpayers ultimately live with this trade-off.

Equity appears to be a particular weakness in Australia. It is a problem for economic productivity and growth when current policy settings inhibit the formation of human capital. A simpler, more equitable and more targeted allocation of federal, state and territory government resources could address this problem. But political realities have made this hard to achieve. On a smaller scale, there have also been several studies in Australia in support of interventions to implement specific pedagogical methods or extracurricular programs to assist in the development of disadvantaged students, including Indigenous students.

Research shows that increased investment in early childhood education improves a variety of longer-term outcomes. Australia seems to do well by this metric. However, some researchers have suggested that it could commit funds in a longer-term manner, as it does for other education sectors.

Finally, the Australian government's recent policy focus on STEM education shows an interest in designing an internationally competitive education system that meets the needs of the future. However, there are concerns that the government's investment in STEM education is not targeted enough and comes at the expense of non-STEM areas, many of which are increasingly valued in the labour market. More employment data, more understanding of that data and more communication to the public is required regarding which parts of STEM are experiencing a skills shortage and which are not. Researchers seem to agree that, while STEM is important at all levels of education, the approach should be specific to the individual student. Other skills such as soft skills and critical thinking should not be neglected, and education strategies should include a greater focus on the entire trajectory of a student's development, especially at the early childhood stage, rather than just upon exiting school.

Summary of Findings

Overall, this case study has shown that the question of which education policies best improve student outcomes is an area of active research and debate. Policies must be designed in the context of a particular education system. The largest net benefits appear to come from policies which are targeted towards individual school, teacher and student needs. Developing such policies requires a strong evidence base.

In this case study, we:

- outlined ways in which student outcomes can be measured. The most common measures are based on standardised test scores, but we should also consider future income and other dimensions of wellbeing. (Chapter 2)
- examined the relationship between wellbeing and other measures of student outcomes, which is positive and mutually reinforcing. On a societal level, there are positive effects on income and wealth, economic growth, civic participation, and equity and social mobility. (Chapter 3)
- explained the rationale for government intervention in education. Government intervention is motivated by the significant social benefits of education, and the tendency of private markets to undersupply as market participants do not factor these positive externalities into their decision making. (Chapter 4)
- discussed policies to improve student outcomes in developing countries, focusing on examples of education subsidisation and decentralisation. In both example studies, results were positive but did not always reach more disadvantaged students. This motivates further interventions to correct institutional weaknesses and address the needs of individual students. (Chapter 5)
- discussed policies to improve student outcomes in developed countries, focusing on teacher incentives and school accountability mechanisms. Financial incentives for teachers tied to student outcomes appear not to work that well. School accountability policies seem to improve student outcomes but potentially with negative equity effects. Better alternatives to these policies may include: improving teacher quality with higher base pay and more flexible performance management, and focusing school accountability on student growth rather than absolute performance. (Chapter 6)
- reviewed student outcomes and policies to improve student outcomes in Australia. Australia's international rankings in standardised tests have been declining. The policy approach could benefit from: a focus on evidence-based teaching practices, better school accountability mechanisms, and a targeted approach to school funding. (Chapter 7)

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